

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D2.9 Underwater Thematic Services Assessment Report

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D2.9 Underwater Thematic Services Assessment Report

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Abstract

This document is a final overall report on the assessment and evaluation of the NEANIAS UNDERWATER services mainly from user perspective, but also including their technical assessment. Assessment and evaluations processes have been performed for each of the UNDERWATER services release cycles (from release #1 to the latest release #3) involving users internal to the NEANIAS consortium as well as external to the consortium, mainly belonging to academic and research institutes. Also, user feedbacks have been collected and, finally, a technical assessment has been performed thanks to template checklists made available by WP7.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

The NEANIAS WP2 “Underwater Thematic services” is focused on designing three (3) services, addressing a large diversity of tasks within the field of underwater surveys. The underwater services provide a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions and industrial stakeholders, e.g. maritime archaeologists, geologists, biologists, engineers working on offshore construction and stakeholders focusing on environmental damage assessment, etc.

The first Underwater Thematic Service, “Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data service (UW-BAT)”, delivers an advanced, user-friendly, cloud-based version of the popular open-source MB-System software for post-processing bathymetry through Jupyter notebooks with additional functionalities.

The second Underwater Thematic Service, “Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data service (UW-MOS)”, provides an operational solution for large area mapping (in the order of tens of thousands of images) of the seafloor, also addressing visibility limitations from the underwater medium.

The third Underwater Thematic Service, “Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data service (UW-MAP)”, delivers a user-friendly cloud-based solution integrating cutting-edge machine learning frameworks for mapping several seabed classes, validated for archaeological, geo-hazards, energy, and other applications.

1.2 Content and rationale

The deliverable, D2.9, comprises the details of the testing and assessment processes performed on the Underwater Research Services for each release cycle from release #1 to the latest release #3.

The service assessment has been performed owing to the evaluation rounds involving internal and external users internal to the NEANIAS consortium, mainly affiliated with academic and research institutes. Furthermore, user feedback has also been collected.

1.3 Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows. Chapter 2 presents the overall assessment process, like the methodology, the user feedback form, and the assessment rounds for all the thematic services throughout the development process of the NEANIAS release cycles.

Chapter 3 demonstrates the use cases assessed for each Underwater service delivered within the NEANIAS. Chapter 4 reports the results of the assessment process, user feedback and technical assessment. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes this report with a summary of achievements, discussing major issues discovered and outlining future steps to accomplish the final assessment.

2. Assessment Process Overview

2.1 User Assessment Methodology

The user assessment and validation has been performed through the definition of a list of Use Cases with a series of defined steps. The lists have been provided by means of forms (file-based MS Word forms for release #1 and NEANIAS Nextcloud-based forms for releases #2 and #3) that have to be filled by the end users (Table 1) [1] [2] [3].

Underwater Service	Release #1	Release #2	Release #3
UW-BAT	Use case definition	Nextcloud forms integrated with the service	Nextcloud forms integrated with the service
UW-MOS	Use case definition	Nextcloud forms integrated with the service	Nextcloud forms integrated with the service
UW-MAP	Use case definition	Nextcloud forms integrated with the service	Nextcloud forms integrated with the service

Table 1 User Assessment Methodology for each service release.

The definition of each form followed the following template:

- *Service validation title*
- *Project Name* (e.g. NEANIAS UNDERWATER)
- *Module Name* (e.g. UW-MOS Service)
- *Release Version* (e.g. v1.4)
- *Dependencies* (e.g. libopengl0)
- *Requirements* (e.g. Internet Access, MacOS or Ubuntu OS)
- *Service Access* (list of links to access the service, documentation and any multimedia demo)
- *Validation Designed by* (name of the person preparing the form)
- *Last update* (date of the last update of the form)

Then a list of use cases was provided to describe a service functionality to be validated, according to the following template:

- *Use case code* (e.g. TEST-UW-MAP-001)
- *Description* (use case description)
- *Preconditions* (any needed precondition e.g. own a Microsoft or Google account to authenticate)

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- *Steps description* (list of steps required to validate the use case)
- *Steps expected result* (list of expected results for each aforementioned step, reply is OK or ERROR)
- *Notes on Use Case* (free text form to add any additional note or feedback regarding the use case)

Finally, the form presents a free text space to send for any feedback on the overall usage of the service.

2.2 User Feedback Form

Additional feedback from users was collected thanks to a user feedback form, provided by each service and collecting the following information:

- *Domain level of expertise*
- *UI Experience*
- *Result Evaluation*
- *Performance Evaluation*
- *Willingness to recommend the service*

2.3 User Assessment rounds

User assessment rounds to collect information regarding services validation and assessment together by any feedback from the user point of view have been performed for each service release and one additional assessment has been performed before the mid-term review and included in Release #2.

Underwater Services Releases	Production date	User assessment round
Underwater Thematic Services Release #1	31/10/2020	From Sept. to Oct. 2020
Underwater Thematic Services Release #2 (UW-MOS, UW-MAP)	12/10/2021	From Jun. to Oct. 2021
Underwater Thematic Services Release #2 (UW-BAT)	31/03/2022	From Jan. to Mar. 2022
Underwater Thematic Services Release #3	24/08/2022	From Mar to Jun. 2022

Table 2: User Assessment rounds for each service release.

Additional validation sessions have been linked to the workshops/webinars organized for each of the services and reported in the following Table 3 [4]

Underwater Thematic Service	Webinar Title	Date
ALL	<i>NEANIAS Innovation workshop</i>	Oct 26 th 2022
ALL	<i>NEANIAS workshop at Fisheries and Aquaculture department of University of Patras</i>	Oct 19 th 2022
ALL	<i>1st International Conference of Mediterranean Harbour and Coastal Archaeology 2022</i>	Sep 29 th 2022
ALL	<i>NEANIAS Open Innovation workshop</i>	Sep 5 th 2022
U3	<i>Workshop on Artificial Intelligence for Big Satellite Data (follow-up hands on event)</i>	26 Feb. 2021
U3	<i>Hands on Workshop at the National Technical University of Athens</i>	3 Nov. 2021
U3	<i>Seminar on Cloud-based Geospatial Services, RSLab NTUA</i>	3 Oct. 2022

Table 3 Series of webinars organized by WP2 NEANIAS Underwater where user feedback and service assessment have been collected.

2.4 Technical Assessment

Service technical assessment has been performed thanks to discussion and templates furnished by WP7 [5]. Covered areas are related to **service development** (including software development, testing, security aspects, data handling and integration to core services) and **service operation** (including Documentation, Ticketing, Helpdesk, Monitoring, Deployment, Security, Licensing and Service Level Agreement). A list of questions for each assessment area and aspects have been defined as a checklist to be filled by service providers and are presented:

Development

Software Development

- Is the software designed and implemented using a SOA?
- Is a version control system used?
- Source code branch management defined and applied?
- VM/docker images available (if needed)?
- Is any static program analysis tool applied?

Testing

- Is Continuous Integration methodology applied?
- Is Continuous Deployment methodology applied?

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- Is unit testing applied?
- Is integration testing applied?
- Have the integration tests been made available in the NEANIAS CI pipelines? Are the Test Scenarios / Use Cases / Acceptance Criteria documented?
- Is acceptance testing applied?

Security

- Are the security technologies identified?
- Are the user's roles identified?
- Is the authentication bypass tested (e.g. brute force attack)?
- Are all data validated before processing?
- Is the password stored in a secure manner (e.g., using hash)?
- Is every expected error condition properly handled?

Data handling

- Is data handling implemented according to FAIR principles?
- Is the service facilitating the discovery, usage, publication of relevant research products in the respective catalogue?

Integration to core services

- Is AAI service integration implemented?
- Is Accounting Service integration implemented?
- Is Logging Service integration implemented?
- Integration to underpinning services target latest stable releases of such services?
- Is the service properly registered in the Service Catalogue?

Operation

Documentation, Ticketing, Helpdesk

- Documentation available?
- Is capacity building material available for the service? (internal / external audience, video, webcasts, tutorials, usage examples, ...)
- Registered in ticketing system?
- Ticketing system used to plan and track intra/inter-service activities and assist the Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle?
- Is Helpdesk provided?
- Is HelpDesk monitored and relevant KPIs tracked and reported on?
- All documents include necessary tracking information?
- All processes followed have been properly defined and documented?

Monitoring

- Are one or more monitoring endpoints implemented?
- Are the monitoring endpoints accessible by the NEANIAS monitoring tools?
- Provided metrics are useful to measure the service target KPIs?
- Are there any alerts related to the service in the NEANIAS monitoring tools?
- The service can be correctly accessed and consumed?

Deployment

- Is the service deployable in HA?

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- If the service is deployed in HA, is the minimal subset of service components needed to keep the service fully and partially operational known?
- A service backup has been planned, implemented and tested?

Security

- Are all reported vulnerabilities under critical level?
- Is sensitive data treated in secure way?
- Are transmissions secured by using some cryptography mechanisms?
- Is the log saved and rotated?

Licensing and Service Level Agreement

- Does the license permit the use case supported by the service?
- Is the service covered by a Corporate Level SLA?
- Has a service-specific Service Level Agreement/Terms of Use been defined for the service?

3. Underwater Thematic Services Assessment Use Cases

This chapter reports on the established use cases to assess the UNDERWATER Services from the user perspective. For the sake of completeness, we report here the latest defined use cases for the latest release (i.e. release #3).

3.1 U1 – Bathymetry Mapping from Multibeam Echosounder Data service (UW-BAT)

The U1 UW-BAT service aims to support post-processing of multibeam echosounder bathymetry and backscatter data. Embedded in an JupyterLab environment the service provides methods based on the MB-System suite. Prepared Jupyter Notebooks allow to run semi-automated processes for editing, correction and creation of maps of bathymetry and backscatter data.

Webpage UW-BAT: <https://bathyprocessing.neanias.eu/>

Documentation UW-BAT: <https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u1-bathyprocessing/en/latest/>

Validation from UW-BAT:

The following table shows the list of use cases defined to validate the UW-BAT service and in particular the functionalities provided and related to MB-System. The mentioned case codes are monitored within the accounting service, once released.

Use Case code	Use Case Description
UC-START-PROCESSING	Utilise various features within Jupyter Notebook
UC-START-MBPREPROCESS	Extracts vendor raw datafile and performs preprocessing of swath sonar data as part of setting up an MB-System processing structure for a dataset
UC-START-MBOTPS	Generate open ocean tidal model for specified time and location using the Oregon State Tidal Prediction Software (OTPS) package
UC-START-MBGRID	Grid bathymetry, amplitude, or sidescan data from swath sonar data files
UC-CREATE-GRID-MAP	Writes a shell script which will generate a GMT map (postscript) of the data based on grids, previously created.
UC-DISPLAY-RESULTS	Generates jpg from postscript and displays the results/maps within Jupyter Notebook
UC-START-MBAREACLEAN	Identifies and flags bad beams in swath sonar bathymetry data within a specified area
UC-START-MBBACKSCATTER	Generates corrections for sidescan and/or amplitude data by calculating average amplitudes as a function of the seafloor grazing angle

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UC-RUN-MBLEVITUS	Create a water velocity profile which is representative of the mean annual water column for a specified 1 degree by 1 degree region
UC-START-MBPROCESS	Process swath sonar data files, including merging navigation, applying bathymetry edits, recalculating bathymetry by raytracing, and applying a variety of other corrections
UC-START-MBINFO	Output basic statistics & meta data of swath sonar data files

Table 4 Use cases related to the UW-BAT service.

3.2 U2 – Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data service (UW-MOS)

The U2 UW-MOS service provides methods to create 2D and 3D maps out of 2D (possibly georeferenced) optical images, as well as related tools to aid in the optical mapping pipeline such as camera calibration, lens undistortion, image enhancement and data quality check.

Webpage UW-MOS: <https://uw-mos.neanias.eu/>

Documentation UW-MOS: <https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service/en/latest/>

Validation form UW-MOS:

In the following table we report the list of use cases defined to validate UW-MOS:

Use Case code	Use Case Description
TEST-UW-MOS-001	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data
TEST-UW-MOS-002	Check image quality using Demo Data
TEST-UW-MOS-002	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data
TEST-UW-MOS-004	Create 3D model using Demo Data

Table 5 Use cases related to the UW-MOS service.

3.3 U3 – Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data service (UW-MAP)

The U3 UW-MAP service provides methods and machine learning (ML) models for seabed classification based on multi-spectral multi-beam echosounder data. Given a multi-spectral backscatter image in TIFF format, the ML model selected by the user is used to produce a seabed classification map of the corresponding area.

Use Case code	Use Case Description
TEST-UW-MAP-001	Classification of “Validation regions” using model and comparison with provided geological maps/bathymetries
TEST-UW-MAP-002	Classification of “Demo regions” using the available models (3-classes, 4-classes and 5-classes)

Table 6 Use cases related to UW-MAP service.

4. Underwater Services Assessment and User Feedback Results

4.1 Underwater Services User Assessment

The following table summarizes the information on the validation of the Underwater Services releases (#1, #2 and #3) and includes: the number of end users validating the service and the evaluation percentage on passed/failed use cases.

Underwater Services	Release #1		Release #2		Release #3	
	Users	Evaluation	Users	Evaluation	Users	Evaluation
U1-UW-BAT*	26	85%	75	9%	106	28%/98%**
U2-UW-MOS	10	100%	0	0	9	100%
U3-UW-MAP	6	67 %	27	100 %	60	98 %

Table 7: Number of end users and results of the evaluation on the use cases to assess the NEANIAS Underwater Services releases (release #1, #2 and #3).

*Note: U1-UW-BAT had delays for release #2 & #3, mentioned and explained in [2] [3]

**Note: Only 28% left a feedback but 98% passed evaluating the service based on the successfully released use cases, documented by the version #3 integrated accounting service.

All the validation procedures for each service and the results of the validation by end users have been collected by NextCloud Forms and are stored on the NEANIAS Documentation Repository in the WP2 area for internal use.

4.2 Underwater Services User Feedback

All the details regarding the received user feedback for all Underwater Services can be found on the previous deliverables regarding the Underwater services validation [1] [2] [3].

4.2.1. U1 – Bathymetry Mapping from MBES Data service (UW-BAT)

Validation and feedback were solicited from potential users and the NEANIAS team and participating end users, respectively. A feedback form, was provided within the service and documentation as a link (<https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/TatpJyZYz5dKK32m>). Nevertheless, much feedback was also provided via email and in numerous chats and discussions.

Since release #3 at the beginning of September 2022, a total of 239 logins were recorded for UW-BAT, conducted by 106 users. 21 users left feedback via our form provided through NEANIAS NextCloud linked under <https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/TatpJyZYz5dKK32m>. 5 users gave feedback through email response.

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Only about 50-55% of the users were, to some extent, familiar with the topic of bathymetric post-processing in one or the other way and were either Hydrographers, Hydroacoustic Engineers, Postdocs, PHD or Students from Marine Sciences, Geo- or Biosciences. Approximately 45% of our users never did hydroacoustic processing. They mainly come from academia (e.g., Students, PHDs, Postdocs) or ambitious and curious persons from other research fields and industries. The cloud service has been especially popular during and after conferences where the project was presented.

	Domain level of expertise		
	Low	High	Expert
Number of users	44%	13%	43%
UI Experience			
Poor	16%		
Satisfactory	41%		
Excellent	43%		
Result Evaluation			
Poor	6%		
Satisfactory	28%		
Excellent	66%		
Performance Evaluation			
Poor	3%		
Satisfactory	55%		
Excellent	42%		
Willingness to recommend			
Unlikely	6%		
Most likely	31%		
For sure	63%		

Table 8 User feedback summary for the 3rd release of the UW-BAT service.

4.2.2. U2 – Seafloor Mosaicking from Optical Data service (UW-MOS)

Currently, UW-MOS counts 203 unique users mainly from academia (experts in areas such as computer vision, archaeologists, geologists, roboticists), but also from companies, and other non-expert users which are simply curious to see what our photogrammetry mapping methods can offer.

Feedback from users was collected using the following form at the NEANIAS' NextCloud instance (data sharing core service):
<https://files.neanias.eu/apps/forms/5ENEY6rZWA4W9ypT>

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While not many users answered our user-feedback form, overall, the user experience is good (12% found it *Satisfactory* and 88% *Excellent*), the results are considered as Excellent by all the surveyed users, and performance of the service is also perceived as good (25% found it *Satisfactory* and 75% *Excellent*). A summary table joining all the responses of the users is shown in Table 9

	Domain level of expertise		
	Low	High	Expert
Number of users	3	2	3
UI Experience			
Poor	0%		
Satisfactory	12%		
Excellent	88%		
Result Evaluation			
Poor	0%		
Satisfactory	0%		
Excellent	100%		
Performance Evaluation			
Poor	0%		
Satisfactory	25%		
Excellent	75%		

Table 9 User feedback summary for the 3rd release of the UW-MOS service.

4.2.3. U3 – Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data service (UW-MAP)

At the submission of this deliverable, the UW-MAP service counts 237 unique users, 56 of which have used the service more than once (returning users). Most of these users (~90%) are external users, many of which are affiliated with universities and research institutions around the globe, as well as companies that operate on relevant sectors.

In total, more than 100 users have provided feedback regarding the service usage, either through the work validation forms (first validation round), or through the NEANIAS Nextcloud User Feedback forms. The user experience, assessed through the analysis of these forms, is predominantly positive and the vast majority of the users would reuse the service and are willing to recommend it to other potential users, as can be seen in Table 10 below.

	Domain level of expertise		
	Low	High	Expert

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Number of users	24	46	2
UI Experience			
Poor	0%	4%	0%
Satisfactory	87%	68%	50%
Excellent	13%	28%	50%
Result Evaluation			
Poor	0%	4%	0%
Satisfactory	71%	72%	100%
Excellent	29%	24%	0%
Performance Evaluation			
Poor	33%	17%	0%
Satisfactory	29%	52%	50%
Excellent	38%	31%	50%
Willingness to recommend	Yes (23/24)	Yes (45/46)	Yes (2/2)

Table 10 User feedback summary for the 3rd release of the UW-MAP service.

5. Summary

This document presents a final overview on the assessment and evaluation processes of the NEANIAS UNDERWATER services. It summarizes the main outcomes of a continuous evaluation of the services from a final user perspective, as well as a detailed technical assessment performed according to the templates provided by WP7, focusing on development and operational aspects.

Assessment and evaluations processes have been performed for each of the UNDERWATER services release cycles (from release #1 to the latest release #3) involving users both internal and external to the NEANIAS consortium. The user base covered a wide range of technical backgrounds, with most users belonging to academic and research institutes and having different levels of expertise (from students to senior scientists).

User feedback has been collected thanks to engagement events using different means, mailing lists, webinars, workshops, and conferences. This feedback has provided useful insights that have allowed us to progressively improve the services, enhancing availability, stability and user experience until reaching TRL8 and onboarding on EOSC.

References

- [1] NEANIAS,. WP2, «D2.4: Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1,» 2020.
- [2] NEANIAS, WP2, «D2.6: Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #2,» 2022.
- [3] NEANIAS, WP2, «D2.8: Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #3,» 2022.
- [4] NEANIAS, WP7, «D7.9: Training & User onboarding activities report,» 2022.
- [5] NEANIAS,.WP7, «D7.3: Software Assessment Methodology,» 2020.

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
H2020	Horizon 2020
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package